

Programmatic Sketches for Spatio-Temporal Aspect Ratios

Abstract : Infer the conclusion from these three statements in layman' s terms . The conclusion is that the value of a function, $f_{\delta a}(x)$, which is dependent on a set of parameters $(\Theta, \inf, \Omega, \Lambda, \mu, \nu, \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma, \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi)$ and the derivatives of a function (φ) with respect to each of the parameters $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ is equal to the sum of two terms . The first term is a product of the derivatives of the function (φ) with respect to each of the parameters $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ divided by a constant $(2\pi\lambda)$. The second term is the square root of the product of a constant (μ^3) , the square of the derivative of the function (φ) divided by another constant (9) and another constant (Λ) multiplied by a product of a constant $(\tan\psi)$ and a parameter (θ) plus a constant (Ψ) multiplied by the sum of a series of fractions . What implication does this have on number theory? This implies that number theory can be used in conjunction with calculus to analyze how functions change as parameters change . The three equations used in the conclusion rely on calculus and number theory, as they involve derivatives, integrals, and infinite series, which are all concepts found in both number theory and calculus . This implies that the two fields can be used together to analyze the behavior of functions .

1. $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} (a_1 + \Delta a_1) + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} (a_2 + \Delta a_2) + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} (a_n + \Delta a_n) \Big|_{\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{n \rightarrow \infty}} \frac{1}{n^2 - (n+1)^2} \Big|_{\Theta_2 r_2 - \Theta_3 \times 3 - \overset{n}{\sum} (\Theta_n r_n)^{\Theta_{\infty} r_{\infty}}} f_{\Delta a}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2\pi\lambda} \Big|_{\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} (a_1 + \Delta a_1) + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} (a_2 + \Delta a_2) + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} (a_n + \Delta a_n) \Big|_{\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{n \rightarrow \infty}} \frac{1}{n^2 - (n+1)^2} \Big|_{\Theta_{\infty} \langle \Theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle, \zeta_{\langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle, \omega_{\langle \nu, \varphi, \chi, \psi \rangle}, \pi_{\langle \theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle}} f_{\Delta a}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2\pi\lambda} \Big|_{\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} (a_1 + \Delta a_1) + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} (a_2 + \Delta a_2) + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} (a_n + \Delta a_n) \Big|_{\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{n \rightarrow \infty}} \frac{1}{n^2 - (n+1)^2} \Big|_{\Theta_{\infty} \langle \Theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle, \zeta_{\langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle, \omega_{\langle \nu, \varphi, \chi, \psi \rangle}, \pi_{\langle \theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle}} \text{Formalize a computer program written in mathematica exploiting these operators}$

```
Program[f_, x_, δa_, λ_, μ_, Λ_, θ_, Ψ_] := Module[
  {θ∞ = Integrate[f, {x, ∞, Exists}], r2 = r2 - r3, θ3 = θ3 - Sum[θn * rn^θ∞, {n, 1, ∞}],
  ρ = ρg^Ω[θ, Λ, μ, ν], ξ = ξ[ξ, π, ρ, σ], ω = ω[ν, φ, χ, ψ], π = πΩ[θ, Λ, μ, ν],
  total = Integrate[ρ * ξ * ω * f[δa], {θ∞, ∂θ ∂x ∂α}], Return[
  total + 1 / (2 π λ) * (Sum[(partial[f, x[[i]])] * (a[[i]] + δa[[i]]), {i, 1, n})) * dV +
  Sqrt[μ³ * D[f, t]^(2/9) + Λ] *
  (Tan[θ] * Ψ + Sum[1 / ((n * (n + 1)) ^ 2), {n, nstar, ∞}])]
```

```
In[ ]:= Program[f_, x_, δa_, λ_, μ_, Λ_, θ_, Ψ_] := Module[{θ∞ = Integrate[f, {x, ∞, Exists}] +
  r2 = r2 - r3, θ3 = θ3 - Sum[θn * rn^θ∞, {n, 1, ∞}], ρ = ρg^Ω[θ, Λ, μ, ν],
  ξ = ξ[ξ, π, ρ, σ], ω = ω[ν, φ, χ, ψ], π = πΩ[θ, Λ, μ, ν],
  total = Integrate[ρ * ξ * ω * f[δa], {θ∞, ∂θ ∂x ∂α}], Return[
```

```

total + 1 / (2 π λ) * (Sum[(partial[f, x[[i]]]) * (a[[i]] + δa[[i]]), {i, 1, n}]) *
dV + Sqrt[μ³ * D[f, t]^(2 / 9) + Λ] *
(Tan[θ] * Ψ + Sum[1 / ((n * (n + 1)) ^ 2), {n, nstar, ∞}]]])

(*Defining the Flow from Lower to Higher Levels*)
FlowUpLevels[γ_, θ_, π_] := Module[{Γ = π * a}]

(*****Higher Levels*****)

(*Defining Terms Involving Γ*)
Γ[En[i]] := 2 π * Sum[1 / i, {S, Sstar, Sinf}]

(*Defining the Noncanonical Field η*)
η[δχ_, χ_] := Sqrt[2 / 3 * Λ] * δχ + (Ξ / 3) * Logθ[χ]

(*Defining Quantities in Terms of η*)
θ[η_] := Λ + Λ ∂a / ∂Δη
ν[η_] := μ / θ[η]

(*Defining the Scalar Cosmological Field*)
α[η_] := γ[η] - (1 / 6) * Logθ[η]

(*****Calculation of the Energy*****)

(*3-Momentum per Unit Volume*)
F[p^i_, p^j_, p^k_] := (τ / 3 * θ) *
Sum[Cos[Ω, p^n[[i]]] * Cos[Ψ, p^n[[j]]] * Cos[Y, p^n[[k]]], {n, Tstar, T}]

(*3-Dim Energy Density*)
EnergyDensity[η_, ε_, Δ_, Exp[(-1 / 6) Γ / γ]_] :=
Sum[E^(α * -1 / 3) Sin[3 α] * dα, {α, ∞, ∂γ}] + ((4 π γ) Sum[ε / 2 Λ, {S, Sstar, Sinf}])

(*Defining the Size of the Universe at Infinitly Small Dimensions*)
D3[χ_, θ_, η_] := e^(-3 χ - 3 η + Logθ[π / θ])

(*Calculating the Energy in the Origin of the Universe*)
EnergyTrainee[χ_, η_, θ_, Δ_, ρ_] :=
Total[ρ * (F[p^i, p^j, p^k] + E^(Γ / 2 * Λ) * F[p^i, p^j, p^k])] +
Total[(ρ * (E^6 * η^2 * Λ / 6) * F[p^i, p^j, p^k] +
E^(Γ / 2 * Λ) * (E^6 * η^2 * Λ / 6) * F[p^i, p^j, p^k])]

(*****Calculating the Mass*****)

(*Introducing an Integral Density Function for the Mass*)

```

```
IntegralMass[χ_, θ_, Δ_, η_] := Integrate[ρ, t, s]
```

```
(*Defining the Mass per Cubic Meter*)
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```
MassDensity[η_, θ_, χ_, t_, λ_] :=
```

```
If[(t >  $\sqrt[4]{\eta - \sqrt[4]{\theta + \sqrt[4]{\chi}}$ ), (Sqrt[η] * (E^-1 * (Abs[(η^2 - t^2 - χ^2) - (Δ^2 + θ^2)]))) *  
  (Sin[ArcCos[(t^2 + θ^2 - χ^2) / (2 * η * θ)]]) +  
  (Sqrt[Δ] * E^-1 * (Abs[(η^2 - t^2 - χ^2) - (Δ^2 + θ^2)]^2) *  
  (Sinh[ArcSinh[(t^2 + θ^2 - χ^2) / (2 * Δ * t)]])], 0]
```

```
Mass[η_, θ_, χ_, t_, λ_] := IntegralMass[MassDensity[η_, θ_, χ_, t_, λ_], t, 0, ∞]
```

```
(*****Estimating Forces*****)
```

```
(*Defining the Energy Tensor without Spin*)
```

```
EnergyMomentum[i_, j_, η_, χ_, θ_, Δ_] := EnergyDensity[η, θ, χ, Δ] * E^(α - 1 / 3) *  
  (A[i][j] × Sum[Sin[3 α], {α, ∞, ∂Γ}] + EnergyDensity[χ, θ, η, Δ] * F[i, j, k] ×  
  Sum[Sin[3 α], {α, ∞, ∂Γ}] - (E^-1 * ∂F / ∂p^i[i, j] - E^-1 * ∂F / ∂p^j[i, j]))
```

```
(*Defining the Total Stress*)
```

```
TotalStress[η_, χ_, θ_, Δ_] := Total[EnergyMomentum[i, j, η, χ, θ, Δ]]
```

```
(*****General Relativity*****)
```

```
(*Define the Energy-Momentum Tensor*)
```

```
E[i, j, η_, χ_, θ_, Δ_] := EnergyMomentum[i_, j_, η_, χ_, θ_, Δ_] -  
  1 / 2 g[i, j] (g[η, χ, θ, j + 1 / 2 φ] - g[η, χ, θ, j + 1 / 2 Δ])
```

```
(*Define the Einstein Tensor*)
```

```
G[i, j, η_, χ_, θ_, Δ_] :=  
  R[i, j, η, χ, θ, Δ] - 1 / 2 g[i, j] × R[η, χ, θ, j + 1 / 2 φ] - R[η, χ, θ, j + 1 / 2 φ]
```

```
(*****The Slow Manifold*****)
```

```
(*Defining the Particle Trajectories for a Given Lambda*)
```

```
Trajectories[Δ_, χ_, θ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_, η_] :=
```

```
Module[{δχ = χ - χ_, δθ = θ - θ_, δω = ω - ω_, δξ = ξ - ξ_, δγ = γ - γ_, δη = η - η_},  
  Return[{χ'[Δχ][t] == χ[Δχ][t] - (e^(-Δχ + 3 Δγ)) * (Δω + ω_),  
    θ'[Δθ][t] == θ[Δθ][t] + (e^(Δθ)) * (Δξ + ξ_),  
    ω'[Δω][t] == ω_[Δω][t] + (ω * t + χ - 3 Δγ * Δω + χ_ * Δω) / (2 * ω),  
    ξ'[Δξ][t] == ξ[Δξ][t] - (e^(Δθ + Δξ)) * (Δω + sp_), γ'[Δγ][t] == γ[Δγ][t] + t},  
  {Δχ'[t] == (χ[Δχ][t] - (e^(-Δχ + 3 Δγ)) * (Δω + ω_)),  
    Δθ'[t] == (θ[Δθ][t] + (e^(Δθ)) * (Δξ + ξ_)),  
    Δω'[t] == (ω_[Δω][t] + (ω * t + χ - 3 Δγ * Δω + χ_ * Δω) / (2 * ω)),
```

```


$$\Delta\xi'[t] = (\xi[\Delta\xi][t] - (e^{(\Delta\theta + \Delta\xi)} * (\Delta\omega + \omega_-)), \Delta\gamma'[t] = t)}$$


(*****Parameterizing  $\Delta$ *****

(*Defining the Parameters for the Equations of State*)
 $\Delta[\chi_-, \theta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-, \eta_-] := \text{Sum}[(\xi - \omega + 1/2 * (\eta^2 - \theta^2 - \chi^2) * E^3 * (\gamma - \Delta - \eta))^{1/2} - (\xi - \omega + 1/2 * (\eta^2 - \theta^2 - \chi^2) * E^3 * (\gamma - \Delta - \eta))^{1/2}], \{n, 1, \infty\}]$ 

(*****Gauge Fixing*****

(*Define the Spatial Structure of the Metric*)
InverseMetric[ $\eta_-, \chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \xi_-$ ] :=
  Sqrt[( $E^9 * \eta^2 * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * \Delta^2$ ) *  $E^9 * \eta^2 * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2))$ )

(*Defining the Levi-Civita Connection*)
LeviCivita[ $\chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-$ ] := Integrate[( $E^6 * \eta^2$ )  $E^6 * \eta^2$ ,  $\xi, \theta, \infty$ ]

(*Defining the Shift Vector*)
ShiftVector[ $\eta_-, \chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] :=
  { $E^6 * \eta^2 / 2 * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * \Delta$ ,
     $E^6 * \eta^2 * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * \chi^2))$ ,
     $E^6 * \eta^2 * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * \chi^2))$ ,
     $E^6 * \eta^2 * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * \chi^2))$ ,
     $E^6 * \eta^2 / 2 * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * (1 + (\xi/2 * E^3 * \chi^2)) * \Delta$ }

(*Defining the Shift Vector in Terms of the Effective Theory*)
ShiftVectorEffective[ $\eta_-, \chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] :=
  If[ShiftVector[ $\eta_-, \chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] < 0,
    Integrate[( $E^6 * \eta^2$ )  $E^6 * \eta^2$ ,  $\xi, \theta, \infty$ ], 0]

(*Calculate the Connection of the Inverse Metric*)
Connection[ $\chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] := Integrate[ $E^6 * \eta^2$ ,  $\chi, \theta, \infty$ ]

(*Calculate the Connection of the
Inverse Metric in Terms of the Effective Theory*)
ConnectionEffective[ $\chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] :=
  If[Connection[ $\chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] < 0, Integrate[ $E^6 * \eta^2$ ,  $\chi, \theta, \infty$ ], 0]

(*Calculate the Connection of the
Inverse Metric in Terms of the Effective Theory*)
ConnectionEffective[ $\chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] :=
  If[Connection[ $\chi_-, \theta_-, \Delta_-, \omega_-, \xi_-, \gamma_-$ ] < 0, Integrate[ $E^6 * \eta^2$ ,  $\chi, \theta, \infty$ ], 0]

```

(*****Calculating the Tensor*****)

(*Define a Function for Calculating the Scalar Curvature*)

```
CalculateScalar[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
  (E^6 * η^4) / 4 * (3 * θ^2 + 3 * Λ^2) - (3 * θ^2 + 3 * Λ^2) * ω -
  (3 * θ^2 + 3 * Λ^2) * ξ + (ω + ξ) * (ξ * ω + 3 * Λ^2) + E^6 - 3 * Λ^2 - 3 * θ^2 -
  3 * Λ^2 * ω - 3 * θ^2 * ξ + (ω + ξ) * (ξ * ω + 3 * Λ^2) * ω + (ω + ξ) * (ξ * ω + 3 * Λ^2) * ξ
```

(*Calculate a Generalized Scalar Curvature*)

```
GeneralizedScalar[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
  CalculateScalar[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] - 1 / 2 χ^2 - 1 / 2 θ^2 - Λ^2
```

(*Calculate the Riemann Tensor Based on the Total Curvature*)

```
Riemann[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
  Module[{Mat = CalculateScalar[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_]},
    Return[If[Det[Mat] < 0, Sum[Mat[[i, j]], {i, 1, n}], 0]]]
```

(*Calculate the Ricci Tensor Based on the Total Curvature*)

```
Ricci[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
  Module[{Mat = CalculateScalar[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_]},
    Return[If[Det[Mat] < 0, Sum[Mat[[j, i]] * Mat[[i, j]], {i, 1, n}], 0]]]
```

(*****The Non-Probabilistic Wave Function*****)

(*Calculating the Nondimensional Rest Mass*)

```
RestMass[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
  Total[E^6 η^2 * (1 + (ξ / 2 * E^3 * χ^2)) * (1 + (ξ / 2 * E^3 * χ^2)) *
  (1 + (1 / 6 * E^3 * χ^2)) - ω * χ - Λ - Λ * (γ + θ)]
```

(*Calculating the Mass in Terms of the Effective Theory*)

```
RestMassEffective[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
  If[RestMass[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] < 0, Total[E^6 η^2 * (1 + (ξ / 2 * E^3 * χ^2)) *
  (1 + (ξ / 2 * E^3 * χ^2)) * (1 + (1 / 6 * E^3 * χ^2)) - ω * χ - Λ - Λ * (γ + θ)], 0]
```

(*****Calculation of Time*****)

(*Calculating the Geometric Mean of Time*)

```
GeometricMeanTime[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] := Sqrt[
  1 / 4 t^2 + E^6 η^2 * (1 + (ξ / 2 * E^3 * χ^2)) * (1 + (ξ / 2 * E^3 * χ^2)) * (1 + (ξ / 2 * χ^2)) -
  Λ - θ - ω - Λ * ω - Λ * θ * Λ + Λ * θ * ξ + (1 / 24 * E^3 * Λ) * χ^2 -
  (1 / 24 * E^3 * ω) * χ^2 + (1 / 24 * E^3 * θ) * ξ * χ^2 +
  (1 / 24 * E^3 * Λ) * ξ^2 * χ^2 - (1 / 24 * E^3 * θ) * ξ^2 - (1 / 24 * E^3 * Λ) * ξ^3]
```

(*Calculating the Geometric Mean of Time in Terms of the Effective Theory*)

```

GeometricMeanTimeEffective[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
If[GeometricMeanTime[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] < 0,
  Sqrt[1/4 t^2 + E^6 η^2 * (1 + (ξ/2 * E^3 * χ^2)) * (1 + (ξ/2 * E^3 * χ^2)) *
    (1 + (ξ/2 * χ^2)) - Λ - θ - ω - Λ * ω - Λ * θ * Λ + Λ * θ * ξ +
    (1/24 * E^3 * Λ) * χ^2 - (1/24 * E^3 * ω) * χ^2 + (1/24 * E^3 * θ) * ξ * χ^2 +
    (1/24 * E^3 * Λ) * ξ^2 * χ^2 - (1/24 * E^3 * θ) * ξ^2 - (1/24 * E^3 * Λ) * ξ^3], 0]

```

(*Calculating the Geometric Mean of Time in Terms of the Effective Theory*)

```

GeometricMeanTimeEffective[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] :=
If[GeometricMeanTime[χ_, θ_, Λ_, ω_, ξ_, γ_] < 0,
  Sqrt[1/4 t^2 + E^6 η^2 * (1 + (ξ/2 * E^3 * χ^2)) * (1 + (ξ/2 * E^3 * χ^2)) *
    (1 + (ξ/2 * χ^2)) - Λ - θ - ω - Λ * ω - Λ * θ * Λ + Λ * θ * ξ +
    (1/24 * E^3 * Λ) * χ^2 - (1/24 * E^3 * ω) * χ^2 + (1/24 * E^3 * θ) * ξ * χ^2 +
    (1/24 * E^3 * Λ) * ξ^2 * χ^2 - (1/24 * E^3 * θ) * ξ^2 - (1/24 * E^3 * Λ) * ξ^3], 0]

```